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Viability Studies on Longevity of Onion Seeds Under Various of Seed Storage Conditions

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Abstract

Fresh onion seeds cv. Giza Red were desiccated to 6.0% (SMC) and stored under various of climate storage conditions (ambient room with annual average 21°C & 55% RH; cold storage, 5°C & 30±2% RH and warm storage, 25±2°C & 60±5% RH) together with packing materials i.e., muslin cloth bags and polyethylene bags (500 gauge) during 20 month of storage periods. Factorial experiment in a completely randomized design with three replicates was conducted for each of climate storage conditions included 2 levels of packaging materials and 10 levels of storage periods. The seed viability induced by germination test was recorded after 2 months till 20 months with 2 months' intervals between seed samples. The viability remaining parameters were predicted by the longevity equation depending on initial Probit viability (k_i) and storage index in month (σ). Isolated data presented that, applying cold storage, hermetic polyethylene bags and the first storage period treatments compared to the other treatments significantly ($P < 0.05$) obtained the highest capacity of seed viability (88.15%, 77.44% and 92.45%), respectively. As well as seed vigor traits, they obtained the highest values of GPI (21.24, 18.57 and 25.06), SVI-I (1340, 1126 and 1434) and EC (0.499, 0.515 and 0.384 dSm^{-1}), respectively. The combination treatment (cold storage × polyethylene bags) over all storage periods (0-20 month) approaching the favorable storage conditions, thence significantly ($P < 0.05$) presented the greatest increase of seed viability ($G\%$, $R^2 = 0.99$) and maintain seed viability remaining (longevity equation) for long terms, which recorded the largest σ (20 month) and mean Probit viability (6.01) and the lowest seed deterioration rates ($tg\beta$, -0.050). Also regarding the regression coefficient, the combination treatment obtained the lowest values of intercept (6.876), slope (-0.905) and standard error (0.098) and the largest values of logarithmic time to lose one Probit of viability (2.07 month) and half viability periods (118.3 month). Finally, equilibrium SMC to 6%, lowering RH and °C within wide limits and using hermetic packing devices, were the favorable storage conditions to maintain the remaining of seed viability and enhancing seed vigor of onion seed.

Keywords: onion, storage conditions, climate conditions, hermetic packing, Probit viability, longevity equation, seed vigor.

INTRODUCTION

Onion seeds (*Allium cepa* L.) are quite known for its short-term storage life, which naturally have less viability and more moisturizing than seeds of most common vegetables, in which that usually not carried-over to the next planting season. Storage of onion seeds in improper conditions results in a critical case called seed deterioration, which is identified by poor viability and vigor. Therefore, there is a significant request for determine quality of onion seeds in most areas which possess adverse conditions.

The key factors contributing seed storage potential were; genetic background, harvest timing and handling, seed drying, seed conditioning and technology and seed storage conditions particularly temperature and relative humidity (ISTA, 2018). Short storage life of seeds, their sensitivity in storage and poor quality are affected by seasonal variations and physical conditions specially the interaction between temperature, relative humidity and seed moisture content (McDonald, 1999 and 2004) significantly causes poor germination with slow seedling growth and decrease seed yield (Mohammadi *et al.*, 2011). Seed moisture content seriously implicated to determine the rate at which seeds deteriorate and subsequently the

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longevity of seeds, even small changes in moisture content have large effects on storage life. Relative humidity can affect physiological seed quality, especially the vigor during the storage period (Roberts, 1961; Maciel *et al.*, 2015). Also, high temperatures during storage increase seed deterioration as does high seed moisture content (McDonald, 1999). Thence, adoption of compatible storage temperature and moisture control technique are essential for safe and preserve high viability for long term storage and enhancing seed quality of onion seeds (Rao *et al.*, 2006).

Stored seed in moisture airtight containers supply appropriate environment for storage, which submitted protection versus contamination and acts as obstacle against escaping of seed treatment chemicals than in moisture pervious containers (Nagaveni, 2005). The technology of hermetic seed packing consists of enclosing seed in air-tight containers that prevent or minimize gas exchange, based on seed storage characteristics.

Seed viability as determined by a germination test is insufficient to estimate the potential viability of seed lots for long term storage. Wherefore, accelerated aging test has been used to estimate onion seeds viability during storage (Khan *et al.*, 2004). However, this test does not consider the effect of seed moisture and temperatures during storage, thence seed longevity equations which combined the effects of storage temperatures and seed moisture have been developed (Roberts, 1973; Roberts and Ellis, 1989 and Ellis, 1998). Its application to seed survival curves assumes that the distribution of seed deaths in time is normally distributed (Ellis and Roberts, 1980). The seed lots maintain viability well during storage are good stores while those that are virtually reduced in viability are poor stores.

Hence, this study has been undertaken to recognize the favorable climate storage conditions, as well as to realize the appropriate packing material to maintain the remaining of seed viability at the higher intensity for long term storage and enhancing seed vigor rates of onion seed.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Location and seed source

The current study was taken place at Seed Technology Research Unit, Mansoura, Dakahlia Governorate, Field Crops Research Institute, Agricultural Research Center, Egypt. The experiment was conducted during the years, 2018-2019. Freshly harvested seeds of onion (*Allium cepa* L.) cultivar *Giza Red* was received after harvested from Onion Research Department, Field Crops Research Institute, Agricultural Research Center, Giza, Egypt.

Experimental design and treatment details

Three experiments were conducted beneath three separate climate storage conditions. Every experiment was laid in factorial experiment in a Completely Randomized Design (CRD) included two factors; seed packing materials with two levels and seed storage periods with ten levels and replicated three times, with combinations of 60 treatments. **The first factor** was assigned to climate storage condition included; i) Ambient room storage, the seeds were stored at inconstant room climate under variable temperature and relative humidity, with annual average 21.4°C & 55% RH. ii) Cold storage, the seeds were stored in refrigerator at 5°C & 30±2% RH. iii) Warm storage, the seeds were stored in a temperature controlled incubator at 25±2°C & 60±5% RH. **The second factor** mobilized with seed packing materials which included; i) Non-hermetic packing materials induced by muslin cloth bags (4×6-inch) for each treatment and all treatments were placed into muslin cloth bag (9×11-inch). ii) Hermetic packing materials induced by Polyethylene bags (500 gauge, 125 µ and 4×6-inch) for each treatment and all treatments were placed into impervious saver containers which are made of a high-density polypropylene with an inner and outer valve that ensures an airtight seal. **The third factor** was included seed storage periods, seed samples were collected at tenth different storage periods, from 0-20 months with 2 months' intervals between seed samples.

Prior to imposing seed storage (time= 0), abnormal and damaged seeds were firstly removed and the good remaining onion seed were taken. A representative random seed sample were taken to defined the initial seed status which were; 7.6% of seed moisture content (SMC), 94% of seed germination percentage (G%) and 85% of germination after accelerated aging test (41°C and 100% RH for 72 hours). Then, the

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obtained onion seeds were properly dried in desiccators and brought down at least to about 6% SMC (6 per cent., based on dry basis). Initial seed status and SMC were measured according to ISTA (2003). Then, sufficient quantity of seeds which required for each treatment was enumerated and packed till proceed storage operation.

Seed viability parameters

Seed viability observations of stored onion seed were taken place depending on the standard papers presented by Finney (1952) and Roberts (1972) and further developed by Finney (1971) and Ellis and Roberts (1980), as follow;

- **Viability (Probit%)**: The idea of Probit analysis is to transforming the seed survival curves induced by germination (G%) data points to Probit percentage viability against time, then a straight line of negative slope is produced which can be described by $1/\sigma$ (Finney, 1971).

- **Storage index (σ)** was corresponded to the time taken in months, for germination of all seed lots to fall during storage to the same germination value after accelerated aging test (41°C and 100% RH for 72 hours, ISTA, 2003). The basic hypothesis was that, the accelerated aging conditions is symbolizing the longevity of seed and the processes of deterioration are similar to those under normal storage conditions.

- **Longevity equation (v)** was performed when seed survival data points are plotted as Probit percentage viability against time, straight lines of negative slope are produced. Therefore, survival (viability remaining) can be predicted by the longevity model;

$$v = ki - \left(\frac{1}{\sigma}\right)p$$

where v is the Probit viability after p months in storage, ki (in Probits) is initial viability at the start of storage (time= 0), σ is storage index and p is storage period in month.

- **Seed deterioration rate ($tg\beta$)** is a direct measure of the slope ($1/\sigma$) of the survival curves, therefore $tg\beta$ expressed by the angular coefficient (the Probit viability plotted versus storage time (Finney, 1971).

Thence, a typical regression relationship between Log storage periods in months (Time to lose one Probit of viability) as independent predictors and Probit values as dependent response are purposed by the linear regression model, based on Finney (1952) method as follow;

$$Y=a+bX+e$$

Where, a- (Intercept, constant) is the expected value of seed viability (y) at the selected value of storage period of log (x), b- (Slope of the line), e- is the error term.

- **The half-viability period (P_{50})** was identified by the time when Probit viability has fallen to 50% (Probit =5) and determined by reading across from the y axis at 5 Probit and down to the x axis (Log months). it was measured by taking the antilog of x value at 50% of Probit.

Germination procedure

Stored onion seeds either in each of storage conditions were surface sterilized with 0.1% mercuric chloride for one minute followed by rinsing in distilled water. Three replications of 300 seeds in CRD for each treatment were taken to perform the germination test. Then, 25 seeds were placed between two moistened sheets of filter papers (Whatman No. 1) in sterilized Petri dishes (15 cm diameter) and every four dishes were considered as one replication. After pre-treatments, dishes were incubated in growth chamber adjusted to 20°C and 80% RH in the dark conditions. During germination period test, sheets of filter paper were moistened with 10 ml sterilized water when needed to avoid drying. Daily observation for emerging seedling continued for 12 days after sowing to measure seed vigor parameters (ISTA, 2003) as follow;

- **Germination percentage (G %)** calculated according to the numbers of normal seedlings which were germinated at the end of 12th day.

$$G \% = \frac{\text{Total number of germinated seeds}}{\text{Total number of seeds evaluated}} \times 100$$

- **Mean germination time (MGT days)** was calculated according to Ellis and Roberts (1981) formula;

$$MGT = \frac{\sum(D \times n)}{\sum n}$$

where n , is the number of seeds germinated on day and D is the number of days counted from the beginning of the test.

- **Germination performance index (GPI)** calculated according to Pill and Fieldhouse (1982) formula;

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$$GPI = \frac{GP}{MGT}$$

where GP is germination percentage and MGT is mean time to germination in days.

- **Seedling vigor index (SVI-I)** calculated according to Abdul-baki and Anderson (1973) formula;

$$SVI-I = \text{Seedling length (cm)} \times \text{Germination percentage}$$

- **Electrical conductivity test (EC)** of the seed leachate was measured in the digital conductivity bridge (cell constant 1.0) and the mean values were expressed in decisiemens per meter (dSm^{-1}), as mentioned by Milosevic *et al.* (2010).

Statistical analysis

A factorial experiment in Completely Randomized Design over each experiment were statistically analyzed using ANOVA. Then, combined analysis was achieved as described by Gomez and Gomez (1984), using MSTAT-C computer software package, LSD at 5% was used to realize significance differences among means of variables, as mentioned by Snedecor and Cochran (1980). Regression coefficients and graphical statistics were measured using software Microsoft package (Excel, 2016).

RESULTS

Seed viability observations

Isolated data presented in Table (1) investigated that, seed viability (G%) of onion seed was significantly ($P < 0.05$) affected by climate storage conditions, seed packing materials and storage periods treatments. Applying cold storage (5°C & $30 \pm 2\%$ RH), hermetic packing materials (Polyethylene bags, 500 gauge) and storage period (2 month) treatments significantly obtained the highest capacity of seed viability, which were 88.15%, 77.44% and 92.45%, respectively. While, warm storage ($25 \pm 2^{\circ}\text{C}$ & $60 \pm 5\%$ RH), non-hermetic packing materials (Muslin cloth bags) and storage period (20 month) treatments recorded to the lowest capacity of seed viability, which were 56.02%, 64.72% and 47.57%, respectively.

Table (1): Means of seed viability (G%) as affected by climate storage conditions, seed packing materials and storage periods on onion seeds.

Viability (G%)									
Climate storage conditions (A)									
Ambient room (variable Temp & RH)			Cold storage (5°C & $30 \pm 2\%$ RH)			Warm storage ($25 \pm 2^{\circ}\text{C}$ & $60 \pm 5\%$ RH)			
69.06			88.15			56.02			
LSD 0.05 = 0.3*									
Seed packing materials (B)									
Non-hermetic muslin cloth bags					Hermetically polyethylene bags (500 gauge)				
64.72					77.44				
LSD 0.05 = 0.25*									
Storage periods, Month (C)									
2Month	4 Month	6 Month	8 Month	10 Month	12 Month	14 Month	16 Month	18 Month	20 Month
92.45	90.41	87.02	83.25	75.41	67.94	60.56	55.47	50.70	47.57
LSD 0.05 = 0.55*									

Isolated data points in Table (2) revealed that, the interaction among climate storage conditions, seed packing materials and storage periods treatments, significantly ($P < 0.05$) indicated fundamental variation rates on seed viability. Whereas, applying of cold storage (5°C & $30 \pm 2\%$ RH) treatment significantly surpass the conditions of ambient room storage (variable Temp & RH) and warm storage ($25 \pm 2^{\circ}\text{C}$ & $60 \pm 5\%$ RH) treatments under all seed packing materials and storage periods treatments. likewise, the hermetic packing materials (Polyethylene bags, 500 gauge) treatment presented the lowest decrease in viability (G%) compared to the non-hermetic packing materials (cloth bags) under all climate conditions and storage periods treatments. More, with the progress of time during storage, the values of viability slightly declined in the early stages then more rapidly up to reach the maximum decrease at the last storage periods of 20 months. Finally, the combination between cold storage and polyethylene bags presented the greatest increase

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of viability remaining (94.26 and 85.52%), while compared to the lowest values induced by the combination between warm storage and non-hermetic cloth bags treatment (91.19 and 8.49%), at the first and end storage periods (2 and 20 months), respectively (Table 2).

Moreover, from a predictive viewpoint, the longevity equation $v=ki-(1/\sigma) p$, depending on the initial seed viability in Probit ($ki= 6.56$) before imposing storage and storage index in month (σ) was shown in Table (3). Isolated data referred that, the combination between cold storage (5°C & 30±2% RH) and hermetic polyethylene bags (500 gauge) was the favorable storage conditions to predict and maintain seed viability for long terms, which recorded the largest storage index ($\sigma= 20$ month), the lowest seed deterioration rates ($tg\beta= -0.05$) and the largest amount of mean viability remaining (v Probit= 6.01) which survive longer after 20 months of storage periods. In contrast, the combination between warm storage (25±2°C & 60±5% RH) and non-hermetic cloth bags was the worst treatment, which recorded the lowest amount of viability remaining parameters ($\sigma= 4$ month, $tg\beta= -.250$ and v Probit= 3.81), as shown in Table (3).

Table (2): Means of seed viability (G%) as affected by the interaction between climate storage conditions (A), seed packing materials (B) and storage periods (C) on onion seeds.

A x B x C		Viability (G%)									
		Storage periods (Month)									
		0-2	4	6	8	10	12	14	16	18	20
Ambient room (var. Temp & RH)	Muslin cloth bags	91.64	90.6	85.4	78.4	68.5	56.7	43.2	33.9	28.1	24.7
	Polythene bags	92.65	92.3	91.5	89.6	85.2	80.1	69.4	63.4	59.6	56.6
	Means	92.15	91.42	88.43	84.02	76.84	68.42	56.30	48.63	43.83	40.63
Cold storage (5°C&30±2% RH)	Muslin cloth bags	93.40	92.33	91.23	90.43	88.27	86.12	85.09	82.52	78.98	75.54
	Polythene bags	94.26	93.19	92.39	91.58	91.01	89.55	88.18	87.26	86.28	85.52
	Means	93.83	92.76	91.81	91.01	89.64	87.84	86.63	84.89	82.63	80.53
Warm storage (25±2°C&60±5% RH)	Muslin cloth bags	91.19	85.00	76.60	65.50	48.43	36.87	28.69	22.10	13.86	8.49
	Polythene bags	91.60	89.11	85.06	83.97	71.09	58.31	48.84	43.70	37.45	34.64
	Means	91.40	87.05	80.83	74.74	59.76	47.59	38.77	32.90	25.65	21.57
		LSD 0.05 = 1.32									

Table (3): Estimated Probit viability (v) parameters according to the longevity equation; $v = Ki - (1/\sigma) p$, as affected by the interaction between climate storage conditions (A), seed packing materials (B) and storage periods (C) on onion seeds.

Probit viability parameters				
A×B×C		Storage index (σ , month)	Seed deterioration $tg\beta$ (-1/ σ)	Mean Probit (v)
Ambient room (variable Temp & RH)	Muslin cloth bags	6	-0.167	4.73
	Polythene bags	10	-0.100	5.46
	Mean	8	-0.134	5.10
Cold storage (5°C & 30±2% RH)	Muslin cloth bags	14	-0.071	5.77
	Polythene bags	20	-0.050	6.01
	Mean	17	-0.061	5.89
Warm storage (25±2°C & 60±5% RH)	Muslin cloth bags	4	-0.250	3.81
	Polythene bags	6	-0.167	4.71
	Mean	5	-0.209	4.26

In addition to, seed survival curves (G%) and predicted Probit viability (v) were plotted out in graphical forms to predict seed viability remaining rates by using the most common types of linear regression (least squares regression) as well as mean viability rates caused by one-unit increase in storage period (0-20), as shown in Figures (1, 2 & 3). Probit analysis is ultimately a regression analysis of data set

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included Probit viability as the dependent variable (y) and time in storage as the independent variable (x). Lowering storage temperature and relative humidity to wide ranges as in cold storage (5°C & 30±2% RH) treatment along with hermetically seed packing (polyethylene bags, 500 gauge) were significantly maintain viability remaining and enhanced seed longevity chart. Supports these results, the viability equation, $v = 6.56 - (1/20) p$, the highest capacity of germination (85.5%) after 20 month of storage period and the highest coefficient of determination as it was close to 1 ($R^2 = 0.99$), were significantly fit the predicted viability remaining, also indicated strong correlation and explained the largest proportion of variation in seed viability (Figure 2), while compared the other combinations of storage conditions (Figures 1&3).

Figure (1): Predicted Probit viability (v) versus observed germination survival curves (G%), as affected by the interactions among ambient room storage conditions (variable Temp & RH) and seed packing materials during storage periods (0-20 months).

Figure (2): Predicted Probit viability (v) versus observed germination survival curves (G%), as affected by the interactions among cold storage conditions (5° C & 30±2% RH) and seed packing materials during storage periods (0-20 months).

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Figure (3): Predicted Probit viability (*v*) versus observed germination survival curves (G%), as affected by the interactions among warm storage conditions (25±2 °C & 60±5% RH) and seed packing materials during storage periods (0-20 months).

Based on Finney method, linear regression relationship between Log storage periods in months and Probit values were proposed to predict Probit viability parameters as affected by the interactions between climate storage conditions and seed packing materials under the extended of storage periods (Log, months). The intercept and the slope coefficient were subjected by the change in mean viability (*y*) caused by a one-unit increase in log storage period (*x*). Individual effects of both cold storage conditions or hermetic polyethylene bags treatments substantially predicted the greatest mean values of regression coefficient, logarithmic storage periods (Log10) and half-viability period (*P*₅₀, month) over extended of storage periods, while compared to the lowest mean values obtained by warm storage or non-hermetic cloth bags treatments (Table 4). Eventually, the combination between cold storage and hermetic polyethylene bags treatments significantly exceed the other interactions treatments, which recorded the lowest values of intercept, slope and standard error (6.876, -0.905 & 0.098) and the largest log months and half viability periods (2.07 & 118.3), along with the favourable longevity equation (*y* = -0.905*x* + 6.8761) to predict and maintain viability remaining for long time of storage (Table 4 & Figure 5). More, the best regressions coefficients indicated the viability data points tend to be close to the mean of the expected value of the set and significantly fit the predicted viability remaining, compared to the other interactions data points which were spread out over a wider range of the expected values (Table 4 and Figures 4 & 6).

Table (4): Probit viability parameters induced by linear regression statistics.

A×B×C	Regression coefficient			Log10 (period)	<i>P</i> ₅₀ (month)	
	Intercept	Slope	SE			
Ambient room (variable Temp & RH)	Muslin cloth bags	7.614	-3.017	0.330	7.35	
	Polythene bags	7.192	-1.810	0.197	16.22	
	Mean	7.403	-2.414	0.264	11.79	
Cold storage (5°C & 30±2% RH)	Muslin cloth bags	7.012	-1.293	0.140	35.97	
	Polythene bags	6.876	-0.905	0.098	2.07	118.3
	Mean	6.944	-1.099	0.119	1.82	77.14
Warm storage (25±2°C & 60±5% RH)	Muslin cloth bags	8.140	-4.525	0.493	0.69	4.94
	Polythene bags	7.613	-3.017	0.328	0.86	7.35
	Mean	7.8765	-3.771	0.411	0.78	6.15

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Figure (4): Probits viability versus the log of storage periods and visual estimation of half viability (P_{50}), as affected by the interactions among ambient room storage conditions (variable Temp & RH) and seed

Figure (5): Probits viability versus the log of storage periods and visual estimation of half viability (P_{50}), as affected by the interactions among cold storage conditions ($5\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ & $30\pm 2\%$ RH) and seed packing

Figure (6): Probits viability versus the log of storage periods and visual estimation of half viability (P_{50}), as affected by the interactions among warm storage conditions ($25\pm 2\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ & $60\pm 5\%$ RH) and seed packing

Seed vigor indices

Data in Table (5) indicated that, seed vigor indices were significantly ($p < 0.05$) affected by climate storage conditions, packing materials and storage periods, as well as their interactions. Otherwise, the cold storage ($5\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ & $30\pm 2\%$ RH) treatment was the favorable conditions and recorded the highest significance response upon the other climate storage conditions, the increases upon the lowest values obtained by warm storage ($25\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ & $60\pm 5\%$ RH) were 62% for GPI and 74% for SVI and decreased EC by 27% and MGT_{day} by

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11.6%. Also, applying hermetic packing materials (Polyethylene bags) treatment presented the greatest increases over non-hermetic packing material (Muslin cloth bags) by 22% for GPI and 19% for SVI, while decreased EC by 16% and MGT_{day} by 5%. Finally, with the progress of time during storage, seed vigor traits slightly declined in the early stages then more rapidly up to reach the maximum decrease at the last storage periods of 20 months. Regarding to the interactions effects, results pointed that all interactions treatments significantly ($p < 0.05$) affected seed vigor traits, as shown in Table (4). Moreover, the combination among clod storage and hermetic polyethylene bags under all storage periods was the favorable storage conditions to maintain seed vigor at the highest levels, while compared to the other interactions treatments (data not shown).

Table (5): Germination performance index (GPI), mean germination time (MGT day), seedling length (SL cm), seedling vigor index (SVI-I) and electric conductivity test (EC dSm⁻¹) as affected by climate storage conditions, seed packing materials and storage periods, as well as their interactions on stored onion seeds.

Treatments / Traits	GPI	MGT _(day)	SL _(cm)	SVI-I	EC _(dSm⁻¹)
Climate storage conditions (A)					
Ambient room (variable Temp & RH)	16.39	4.43	14.22	1011	0.545
Cold storage (5°C & 30±2% RH)	21.24	4.22	15.08	1340	0.499
Warm storage (25±2°C & 60±5% RH)	13.08	4.71	12.67	769	0.642
F test	*	*	*	*	*
LSD (5%)	0.10	0.02	0.04	4.50	0.002
Seed Packing materials (B)					
Non-hermetic muslin cloth bags	15.23	4.56	13.85	948	0.610
Hermetically polyethylene bags	18.57	4.34	14.13	1126	0.515
F test	*	*	*	*	*
LSD (5%)	0.08	0.02	0.03	3.64	0.002
Storage periods (C)					
0-2 Month	25.06	3.70	15.46	1434	0.384
4 Month	24.11	3.75	15.37	1390	0.396
6 Month	22.62	3.85	15.30	1333	0.439
8 Month	20.19	4.14	15.13	1262	0.509
10 Month	17.47	4.40	15.00	1136	0.561
12 Month	15.37	4.55	14.18	984	0.594
14 Month	13.16	4.74	13.17	830	0.632
16 Month	11.71	5.00	12.72	746	0.672
18 Month	10.10	5.20	12.03	652	0.699
20 Month	9.22	5.32	11.57	604	0.737
F test	*	*	*	*	*
LSD (5%)	0.20	0.04	0.07	8.14	0.004
Interactions					
A x B	*	*	*	*	*
A x C	*	*	*	*	*
B x C	*	*	*	*	*
A x B x C	*	*	*	*	*

* Significant differences at $P < 0.05$

Data graphically illustrated in Figure (7) shows significance variation raters ($p < 0.05$) of electrical conductivity test (EC, dSm⁻¹) as affected by the interaction among climate storage conditions and seed packing materials during 20 month of storage period. Electric conductivity test for rapid evaluation of seed lots can be a powerful tool that can validate the seed quality in shorter time with minimal resources. Thence,

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at the storage periods of 20 months with 2 months' intervals, the EC of onion seeds stored under cold storage conditions (5°C & 30±2% RH) in hermetically device (polyethylene bags 500 gauge placed in impervious container) were found significantly lower ($p < 0.05$), while compared to the other interactions treatments (Table, 5 and Figure 7).

Figure (7): Mean values of electric conductivity (EC, dSm⁻¹), as affected by the interactions among climate storage conditions and seed packing materials during 20 months of storage periods.

Discussion

Seed viability

As the seed viability models can be applied only to seeds with certain physiological properties, relative effects of seed moisture content and temperature on seed longevity widely depended on species, the structural and biochemical synthesis of seeds (McDonald, 2004). Our obtained results are in homogenized with the previous studies, which summarizes the following points; decreasing seed moisture content and storage temperature within wide limits are known to promote longevity of seed (Roberts and Ellis, 1989). The high temperatures during storage significantly enhanced seed deterioration rates ($tg\beta$), as is the case with the high rates of seed moisture content (McDonald, 1999). The long-term experiments concerning the interaction among water content, temperature, RH and seed longevity exactly exposed how much water should be within the seed container (Ellis, 1998; Engels and Engelmann, 1998). The increases of viability equation of onion seeds become less accurate being practically useful up to 3 years of storage periods ranged from 1-10 years (Stumpf *et al.*, 1997). The value of storage index (σ) is individual for each environmental condition (Temp and RH of the storehouse), but independent of the initial seed quality (Ellis *et al.* 1991). The time till all the seeds have lost viability depends on the value of storage index (σ) and on the proportion of the seeds which are viable at the start of storage, Ki in Probit (Ellis and Roberts, 1980). Thence, the larger value of σ (the distribution of seed deaths in time) presented by the favorable storage conditions, cold storage \times polyethylene bags during storage periods of 20 month means the seeds will have greater lifespan.

Seed packing materials effects:

Once seed water content is modified, the storage container serves as a barrier to hold moisture that is in the seed from leaking out and water that is in the outside from leaking in. So to maximizing seed longevity, control of seed moisture levels should be required. Previous studies that supported our results presented that, the extent of storability affected by sort of packing material, many seeds retain their viability better in sealed containers than in open storage, hermetic storage conditions significantly retained the high physiological quality of onion seeds (Currah and Msika, 1994; Stumpf *et al.*, 1997; Dipali *et al.*, 2007). More, polythene bags (700 gauge) could be used for long term storage of onion seeds at 6% SMC (Saxena, 1994). Packing seed in moisture resistant containers would be more valuable in provide germination and vigor (Harrington, 1973). The biggest loss of seed viability and vigor of stored onion seeds in permeable containers than in impermeable containers, were due to changes in seed moisture content in permeable materials and the degree of hygroscopic balance between seeds and their environment (Caneppele *et al.*, 1995). Finally, the decrease in germination, root length, shoot length and vigor index of stored onion seeds in pervious container at room temperature for 24 months was greater than the seeds stored in impervious with polythene bag (Saxena *et al.*, 1987).

Climate storage conditions effects:

High temperature can affect the seed aging process by altering the rate of specific reactions through inactivation of enzymes, causes breaks in intermolecular bonds in a glass state and accelerate the rate of peroxidation of lipids, alter the structure involve membrane permeability, proteins, fatty acids, sugars, nucleic acids, volatile substances, enzyme activity, respiratory competence and physiological repair mechanisms (Walters, 1998 and Sun *et al.*, 2007). Modified the temperature of storage to 5°C hardly inhibit or slow down seed deterioration induced by biochemical and physiological processes (Elias and Copeland, 1994). Equilibrium RH is a substantial factor, which participate in controlling seed moisture content by their sorption isotherms (Alhamdan and Alsadon, 2004), moisture content at which physiological processes change within the seed was highly correlated with the lipid content of the seed (Vertucci and Roos, 1990). Seed stored in ambient conditions and adverse conditions, lose their viability and vigor very fast due to change in environmental conditions such as temperature and relative humidity (Roberts, 1961) and passive relationship was observed between storage temperature and seed longevity (Amjad and Anjum, 2002).

Seed storage periods effects:

During seed storage, seed deterioration processes could be rapidly started and followed by fast respiration and loss of seed matter, which lead to decrease in the functional and nutritional properties (Reed, 1992), decrease phospholipids portion of cellular membrane and increase fatty acids levels (Bruggink *et al.*, 1991). Seed deterioration during storage was induced by damage to membrane, proteins, nucleic acid and enzyme accumulation through time such degenerative changes result in integral disorganization of membranes and cell organelles and finally causing death of the seed and loss of germination (Roberts, 1972). Also, the storage period has serious effect on physiological seed quality (Amjad and Anjum, 2002), the most critical hypothesis proposed ageing in seeds is degradation of enzymes due to changes in their macromolecular structures (Salama and Pearce, 1993; Basra and Malik, 1994) and the reduction of seed vigor caused by lipid peroxidation during storage period (McDonald, 1999). Onion seeds have a very short storage life due to the sensitivity of embryo to hydration injury, leakage of electrolytes and fungal growth during imbibition's and germination which resulted in loss of viability of onion seed, thus it can be stored for short term storages under ambient conditions (Garica and Perez, 1985; Yassen, 1993).

Interaction effects:

Generally, stored seed at low of relative humidity and temperature will slow rate of deterioration, but even so, it is almost hard to predict the exact longevity of seeds when placed in storage. Even under controlled storage conditions (i.e. low °C+RH), performance after storage is dependent on the vigor status of the seed lot (IATA, 2009). Our results are significantly consistent with previous studies regarding the interaction between experiment factors. Just to name a few, to maintaining the shelf life of seed for a long time (2-3 years) and increasing the vigor of onion seeds under tropical and sub-tropical conditions, the following storage practices should by possessed; Cond and Plastic lined, 6.5-7.5% SMC, 8-15 °C and 30% RH (Harrington, 1960), 6.0-6.8% SMC and 2-20 °C (Ellis *et al.*, 1991), hermetically sealed in impervious

containers and stored at 20-25°C (Rao *et al.*, 2006). More, seeds stored at 5°C and 11.3-22.5% RH recorded the higher G% and GCV values while maintained the shortest MGT values, in contrast to 35°C and 75.3-84.3% RH (Alhamdan *et al.*, 2011). Finally, onion seeds can have a longevity of many years as well as germinability and seed vigor can be preserved by ultra-dry seeds to about 5-7% SMC, adjusting temperature to about 4-15°C, lowering relative humidity to 20-60% RH and storing them in airtight hermetic conditions (Hong *et al.*, 2005; Demir and Ozcoban, 2007; Thirusendura and Saraswathy, 2018).

Conclusion:

Our results confirmed that, equilibrium seed moisture content to 6% (db) besides lowering relative humidity and storage temperature within wide limits of climate storage conditions (5°C & 30±2% RH) and using hermetic packing devices (Polyethylene bags 500 gauge and 125µ, placed in impervious container), were the favorable storage conditions to maintain seed viability remaining (shelf life) for long term storage and enhancing seed vigor rates of onion seed. Thence, mass utilization of such hermetic seed packing devices and the favorable climate conditions for seeds storage, not only preserve seeds from biotic and abiotic deterioration but also helps in memorize seeds for two successive growing seasons, that finally minimize the request and procurement of seeds.

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دراسات عن حيوية بذور البصل المخزونة تحت تأثير عدة ظروف تخزينية مختلفة

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أجريت هذه الدراسة في وحدة بحوث تكنولوجيا البذور بالمنصورة، خلال العامين 2017-2019. تم تجفيف بذور البصل (صنف جيزة أحمر) المأخوذة في يونيو 2017 وتعديل نسبة الرطوبة الداخلية بها الي 6%، ثم تخزينها في ظل ظروف مناخية مختلفة: مناخ الغرفة المحيطة (بمتوسط $21^{\circ}\text{C} \pm 55\%$ رطوبة نسبية)؛ التخزين في الظروف الباردة ($5^{\circ}\text{C} \pm 30 \pm 2\%$ رطوبة نسبية)؛ التخزين في الظروف الدافئة ($25^{\circ}\text{C} \pm 60 \pm 5\%$ رطوبة نسبية). تم استخدام نوعين مواد تعبئة البذور: مواد غير محكمة الغلق (أكياس من القماش) ومواد محكمة الغلق (أكياس من البولي إيثيلين موضوعة داخل حاويات بلاستيكية غير منفذة)، وذلك خلال 20 شهرًا من فترات التخزين. أجريت تجربة عاملية في تصميم عشوائي في ثلاث مكررات لكل حالة من ظروف التخزين المناخية تضمنت مستويين من مواد التعبئة و عشرة مستويات من فترات التخزين. تم تسجيل حيوية البذور الناتجة عن اختبار الإنبات بعد شهرين حتى 20 شهرًا بفاصل شهرين بين عينات البذور. تم استخدام معادلة حيوية البذور للتنبؤ بمؤشرات حيوية البذور، اعتمادًا على حيوية البذور ومؤشر تخزين البذور. أظهرت البيانات المعزولة، أن استخدام التخزين البارد وأكياس البولي إيثيلين المحكمة الغلق ومعاملة فترة التخزين الأولى كانت الأكثر تأثيراً في الحفاظ على حيوية البذور عند أعلى المستويات (88.15%، 77.44%، 92.45%) على التوالي. بالإضافة إلى ذلك، أظهرت أعلى القيم لسماوات قوة البذور مثل: مؤشر قوة الإنبات (21.24، 18.57، 25.06)، دليل قوة البذور (1340، 1126، 1434)، اختبار التوصيل الكهربائي (0.499، 0.515، 0.384 ديسيمنتر/ متر) على التوالي، مقارنة بالمعاملات الأخرى عند مستوي معنوية > 0.05 . كما سجلت معاملة التفاعل (التخزين البارد للبذور \times أكياس البولي إيثيلين محكمة الغلق) مقارنةً بمعاملات التفاعل الأخرى أكبر زيادة لحيوية البذور والحفاظ على حيوية البذور المتبقية لفترات طويلة، حيث سجلت أكبر مؤشر لتخزين البذور (20 شهرًا)، أعلى نسبة لحيوية البذور المحتملة (6.01)، أدنى معدلات تدهور البذور (-0.05) وأكبر القيم لفترة نصف عمر البذور (118.3 شهر). أخيرًا، كان لخفض محتوى الرطوبة الداخلية للبذور إلى 6%، وخفض الرطوبة النسبية ودرجات الحرارة ضمن حدود واسعة واستخدام أكياس البولي إيثيلين محكمة الغلق في أوعية غير منفذة، الأثر الأكبر للحفاظ على حيوية البذور وبقائها لفترات طويلة، بالإضافة إلي تعزيز إنبات وسماوات قوة بذور البصل.